

RESPONSE PAPER 1**LAST NAME: ADELEKE****FIRST NAME: OLUWANIFISE****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical) citations/references.
The author manually inserted as well as used Zotero to insert references.
The author used Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access).
The author used the following software: (MSWord 2019 on MacBook).

The five key concepts:

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1 – 4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5 – 13)
3. American vs British English (EUCLID 2019, 27 – 34)
4. CMS Crib Sheet (EUCLID 2019, 44 – 55)
5. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2019, 56 – 59)

ACADEMIC WRITING, APPROACHES AND TOOLS

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing is an essential aspect of education. The ability to communicate clearly and effectively is a skill every student should possess. It will not only ensure good grades in a degree but can be very valuable to one's career in the future.

The International Academic Writing (ACA-401D) module is a course that covers the skills, qualities and techniques needed to carry out an original piece of research. The materials of study for this period is the ACA-401/ ACA-401D coursepack (2019) revised by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr Kabiru Gulma as well as a 14-minute video on Euclid's Learning Management System (LMS) by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck. It covers a broad range of issues including the basics of essay writing, how to write effectively, plagiarism, the rules and convention of either the American or British form of writing, Latin expressions and abbreviations, and so on. The coursepack has been put in place to serve as a guide to develop, and aid students strive for perfection in their writing techniques.

This response paper aims to submit my findings and interactions about the key concepts in the first session of the ACA-401D module. Some of the critical ideas interacted

with which I will react to in the preceding sections of this paper include the basics of essay writing, plagiarism, the choice of form (whether American or British) and their rules, the Chicago Manual of Style crib sheet, and the Latin Abbreviations and expressions.

2) ESSAY WRITING; START WORK EARLY!

Chapter one of the ACA-401D coursepack addresses the basics of essay writing. The three notable features of an essay are that it addresses a topic, it answers a question, and it is in the context of an argument. Most importantly, however, whatever the essay or paper seeks to address must be supported by evidence (EUCLID 2019, 1).

The process of writing is not a one-step affair but involves several stages. It ranges from starting the essay to researching the topic to organising one's ideas, to actually writing, referencing and finally editing (EUCLID 2019, 1 – 4). Accordingly, writing encompasses the whole pre-planning stage to the editing stage.

The most crucial point for me about writing is starting early. I find that I very often tend to procrastinate when it comes to writing. My procrastination is not as a result of a lack of interest or motivation. It is majorly about my convenience. I often wait until the requisite mood or emotion overcomes me before undertaking an assignment or writing a paper. For instance, I should have written this response paper about a week ago, but I am only just writing it now because I am currently in the mood to do so. I realise that this is not always the best approach. In fact, in most cases, it is a way not to get anything done at all. Sometimes, it may be necessary to act first, and maybe the requisite mood will follow. Altogether, as the study suggests, part of writing successfully and effectively entails starting work early to have enough time to think, research, read and write eventually (EUCLID 2019, 1).

3) PLAGIARISM

It is possible to define plagiarism in many ways. In simple terms, plagiarism is using someone else's work or idea without giving that person due credit. The Oxford University's guide on study skills and training defines plagiarism as the incorporation of someone else's work or idea as one's own without giving due credit or obtaining necessary consent to and from the author or that source of information ('Plagiarism | University of Oxford' n.d.). However it is defined, the bottom line is that as long as someone's work has been imitated and that work has not been acknowledged (whether intentionally or unintentionally), it is plagiarism (Neville 2010, 29).

Throughout my post-secondary education, the importance of correct referencing has always been emphasised. The reason for this is not far-fetched. Anyone who plagiarises commits the offence of intellectual or academic theft and also shows a complete lack of appreciation for the learning process ('Plagiarism | University of Oxford' n.d.). What is more, plagiarism not only undermines one's standard and quality but also holds grave

consequences for one's education or career. It is thus, impossible to overstate the importance of correct referencing.

I think part of what makes students or people in general plagiarise, is first a lack of originality and idea, and also the fear of critiquing a topic or subject matter by people of high academic reputation. Notwithstanding, a crucial part of learning is that one must have the audacity to either develop ideas originally or have the capacity to interact with other opinions and ideas and come to a personal, independent conclusion based on those opinions or ideas ('Plagiarism | University of Oxford' n.d.).

My take away from the chapter on plagiarism is that I need to be very careful and deliberate in writing. Most times, plagiarism does not happen deliberately but could occur through carelessness or negligence. Similarly, the ability to express an idea or opinion is a crucial part of learning which I must not be scared to do especially in writing.

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

During my master's programme in the United Kingdom, my professors jealously guarded against mixing up both forms in writing. It appears that the same caution has been advised on this programme as well by Professor Cleenewerck in the Basic ACA-401 Tutorial video. A critical aspect of the form which I have to take note of is the placement of periods, commas and quotation marks. In the American format, periods and commas are always inside closing quotation marks. For instance, "All A is B" in the American form will be, "All A is B." while in the British format, it will be, 'All A is B'. Similarly, when it comes to footnoting, the American structure takes the following format: punctuation mark, double quote and reference while the British form allows for a choice between an inverted comma, reference and punctuation mark or between an inverted comma, punctuation mark and reference.

In terms of the form, there are several differences, and it will appear that mixing up the forms does not at all seem wrong. However, it is more about what is standard and non-standard. There is no difference between *color* and *colour* or *analyse* and *analyze*. However, this study is about academic writing, and it will seem that there are set rules or conventions on the usage of language (whether American or British) that one must follow.

It is relatively easy to trivialise the details about the two forms (American or British). Nonetheless, to meet the requisite standard of academic writing, this chapter has reminded me of the need to be deliberate and careful in my choice and to avoid a mixture of both forms.

5) THE CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE CRIB SHEET

The Turabian style is a citing and referencing system based on the Chicago style documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003 and developed by Kate Larimore

Turabian. She authored a manual to guide students in citing and referencing when writing research papers (EUCLID 2019, 44).

At the outset, I have been a little uncomfortable with the thought of applying the Turabian style of referencing in my writings. This is because I am very much comfortable and used to the Oxford Standard for Citation of Legal Authorities (OSCOLA). Throughout my undergraduate and postgraduate education in the United Kingdom, the OSCOLA system of referencing was the recommended referencing style. There is a vast difference in terms of format and style.

In the Turabian style, for instance, scholarly abbreviations such as *e.g.*, *i.e.*, etc. may only be used in parenthetical comments and not outside parentheses. It is recommended that they (scholarly abbreviations) are to be spelt out instead. Abbreviations like, *e.g.* (*exempli gratia*) in the text must be spelt out in their full English form. Consequently, to use, *e.g.* in a text, I will have to use 'for example'. While, *i.e.* will be 'that is' in a text or writing (*ibid*).

Furthermore, capitalisation follows three forms, namely full caps, heading caps and sentence caps. Full caps are mostly used to capitalise every character of every word. They are utilised in major headings. Heading caps, on the other hand, are majorly used to capitalise the first character of each word except for articles, prepositions, conjunctions and infinitives. Sentence caps operate on two major points. Firstly, it capitalises the first letter of the first word of the title/heading and of any subtitle/heading and secondly, it operates to capitalise the first letter of any proper nouns. At the same time, every other thing must remain in lower case. There are so many other technicalities, and they are a lot different from the OSCOLA system.

As can be seen, there are minor but important technicalities involved in this style of references. Before studying the coursepack, I was not too sure about how I will quickly adapt to this new style of referencing. However, having gone through the coursepack and having read briefly on the Turabian style, I do not think it will present too much of a challenge, and I suppose I can get accustomed to it all soon. I also discovered a much more detailed guide to the CMS in this link. I intend to get very familiar with it.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

I have always wondered about Latin expressions in academic writing, especially within the context of legal writing which borrows a lot of context from the Latin language. In Nigeria, for instance, although it is gradually being phased out, a great deal of emphasis has always been placed on law students and their use of Latin abbreviations and expressions. Owing to this, most students see it as an opportunity to just fill their write up with a lot of jargons which in the long run makes their writing less transparent and difficult to comprehend. Contrariwise, in the United Kingdom where I had my post-secondary education, as students, we were always discouraged from using Latin abbreviations and expressions unless it was necessary. We were instead advised to write in plain English for the sake of clarity and easy comprehension.

I cannot say for sure if Latin is archaic. Nonetheless, it appears to be an uncommon language. For this reason, I think for the sake of clarity, it makes more sense to use plain and simple English language in academic writing as opposed to the more robust and uncommon Latin abbreviations or expressions which can make writing less transparent and difficult to comprehend. The only exception to the usage of Latin will be where it is necessary to do so. That said, I think it is appropriate in such circumstance(s) to provide a footnote with the required translation.

7) CONCLUSION

The essence of good writing cannot be understated. Depending on the context, there are many reasons why one should aim to write correctly. For a student like me, good writing may secure top grades. For a blogger or a job seeker, the essence may be different. Nonetheless, the overlying essence of writing is to be clear and make meaning to the reader or audience. There are different styles of writing. However, for this programme, what is of significant concern is academic writing. Academic writing can be technical at times. With a lot of rules and conventions, one must be careful to ensure that these rules and conventions are followed.

This session has been fruitful. It has set the ball rolling and reminded me of the need for good writing. In particular, I am impressed with the depth of the coursepack. It has touched on several issues from how to write an essay, to plagiarism, referencing, the form of writing (whether American or British), punctuations and so forth.

I hope that as the days go by, I can take my writing to the next level and also become much more familiar with all of the rules and conventions studied in this coursepack.

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